

Integrated Plithogenic Quantum Decision Making on Smart and Sustainable Electrical Material Selection

Nivetha Martin^{1,2,3*}, Davron Aslonqulovich Juraev^{4,5,6}, Florentin Smarandache⁷, F. X. Edwin Deepak⁸,
P. Sathya^{9,10}, Gabriel XG Yue¹¹

¹ Department of Mathematics Arul Anandar College (Autonomous) Karumathur, Affiliated to Madurai Kamaraj University, India.

² Postdoctoral Department, Turon University, Karshi 180100, Uzbekistan

³ Post Doctoral, Department, International Engineering and Technology Institute; Hong Kong, China, nivetha.martin710@gmail.com.

⁴ Scientific Research Center, Baku Engineering University, Baku AZ0102, Azerbaijan, djuraev@beu.edu.az

⁵ Department of International Relations, Turon University, Karshi 180100, Uzbekistan, juraevdavron12@gmail.com

⁶ Postdoctoral Department, International Engineering and Technology Institute, Hong Kong, China, juraevdavron12@gmail.com

⁷ Department of Mathematics University of New Mexico Gallup, USA, fsmarandache@gmail.com

⁸ Dept. of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, National College of Engineering Kovilpatti, India, edwindeepak85@gmail.com

⁹ Department of Mathematics, G.T.N.Arts College(Autonomous), Dindigul, Affiliated to Madurai Kamaraj University, India

¹⁰ Research Scholar, Department of Mathematics Arul Anandar College (Autonomous) Karumathur, prathisath@gmail.com.

¹¹ Department of Computer Science and Engineering, European University Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus, xgyue@iet.net

*Correspondence: nivetha.martin710@gmail.com

Abstract: The evolving modern electrical and energy systems are driven by the dual characteristics of sustainability and intelligence. The materials are expected to exhibit more efficiency and good performance with low environmental impacts. This paper develops a novel decision-making model integrating Plithogenic logic with a quantum decision-making approach. This newly developed model addresses the constraints of uncertainty and conflicting criteria in the selection of electrical materials. In addition to the attributes of electrical efficiency, economic viability, thermal stability, environmental sustainability and smart system integration, this decision-making model also considers the attribute values to rank the electrical materials classified as conductors, semiconductors, superconductors, insulators and photovoltaic materials. The newly developed model with Plithogenic accuracy functions and principles of quantum uncertainty is more effective in ranking electrical materials. Sensitivity analysis is performed with different degrees of appearance to analyze the ranking results under various scenarios. This work certainly contributes to the development of a more resilient decision-making approach, paving the way for smart and sustainable energy infrastructure augmentation.

Keywords: Electrical materials, Smart, Sustainable, Plithogenic logic, Quantum

List of Abbreviations	
MCDM	Multi-Criteria Decision Making
MARA	Multi-Attribute Ranking Approach
RAM	Ranking of Alternatives Method
PIV	Preference Index Value
MEREC	Method based on Removal Effects of Criteria
FEM	Finite Element Method
COPRAS	COMplex PROportional ASsessment
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
BIM	Building Information Modelling
IoT	Internet of Things
MAIRCA	Multi-Attributive Ideal-Real Comparative Analysis
TODIM	Interactive and Multi-Criteria Decision Making (from Portuguese: <i>Tomada de Decisão Interativa Multicritério</i>)
PROMETHEE II	Preference Ranking Organization METHod for Enrichment Evaluations II
VIKOR	VlseKriterijumska Optimizacija I Kompromisno Resenje (Serbian for “Multi-Criteria Optimization and Compromise Solution”)
MUTLIMOORA	Multi-Objective Optimization on the Basis of Ratio Analysis Plus Full Multiplicative Form
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
MCDM–Pareto ANOVA	Multi-Criteria Decision Making combined with Pareto-based Analysis of Variance
FEA and Ensemble MCDM	Finite Element Analysis combined with Ensemble Multi-Criteria Decision Making

1. Introduction

The increasing growth of smart grids, renewable energy systems and power electronics have caused the selection of electrical materials more intricate. In modern energy systems, the selection of electrical materials requires a balance between the attributes of economic, eco-friendly and technological compatibility for enhancing the performance efficacy. The existence of interdependent and conflicting criteria makes the ranking of the electrical materials more complex. For instance, a material exhibiting high conductivity may be expensive and lack compatibility with smart systems. On other hand the materials with low economic impact may yield poor thermal stability and performance. In general, MCDM methods are applied in choosing the optimal material selection. To mention a few, Van Dua et

al[1] applied the method of MARA, RAM and PIV in material selection for screw shafts, gear manufacturing and lubricants. Kumar et al [2] employed the method of MEREC in coating material selection for bulk metal. Albert and Takacs [3] used the method of FEM in thermoelectric material selection. Mahanta et al[4] applied hybridized methods and Danh [5] employed integrated MCDM methods in selecting cutting tool material. Satapathy et al[6] utilized the method of COPRAS in acoustic material selection. Petkovic and Madic[7] used MCDM solver in wave energy turbine blade material selection. El Hallaoui[8] in selecting building material. Karthikeyan et al[9] applied MCDM–Pareto ANOVA in material selection of alloys. Martinez and Nicolalde[10] employed simulation based MCDM in brake disc material selection. Worku[11] employed multi step integrated MCDM method in construction material selection in formwork material selection. Mohammed Raffic et al[12] used multiple MCDM methods in bracket material selection. Dasgupta et al[13] used entropy-TOPSIS in sustainable polymer composite material selection. Kumar and Pratihari[14] used FEA and ensemble MCDM in biomechanical material selection. Jangam et al[15] applied BIM-MCDM in building envelope material selection. However, these traditional models are not competent in handling complexity, incongruities and ambiguity. This has led to the pathway for developing Plithogenic based decision-making.

Plithogenic multi-criteria decision-making models are highly robust as they are characterized as generalized representations of fuzzy, intuitionistic and neutrosophic models. Smarandache introduced Plithogenic sets as a quintuple of the form (P, a, V, d, c) with P as the set, a is the attribute, V is the set of attribute values, d is degree of appurtenance and c is the degree of contradiction. Plithogenic based MCDM are developed by the researchers to evolve a more comprehensive kind of decision-making models. Abdel et al[16] developed an integrated Plithogenic MCDM for evaluating especially the financial performance of manufacturing industries. Grida et al[17] in assessing the performance of supply chain containing the elements of IoT. Ahmad et al[18] and Ozcil et al[19] conceptualized generalized Plithogenic sets and Plithogenic hypersoft sets based MAIRCA method in making green supplier selection. Huang and Yu[20] applied integrated Plithogenic MCDM in making evaluations of the quality of blended teaching. Sudha et al[21] developed a supplier selection decision making model using combined Plithogenic hypersoft representations. Yang et al[22] utilized Plithogenic decision making framework in evaluating construction products considering the contradictions. Liu et al[23] used Plithogenic approach in evaluating green construction projects. Xing et al[24] utilized Plithogenic RAM in assessing the performance of concrete structures. Fatukasi and Adebisi[25] applied Plithogenic hypersoft sets in optimizing the cryptocurrency investment decisions. These contributions exhibit the efficacy of Plithogenic MCDM in different scenarios.

On other hand, quantum-based ranking is gaining momentum to handle complex decision-making environments. The principles of quantum theory such as superposition and probability amplitudes play an intrinsic role in addressing higher-order indeterminacy, non-linearity and multi-perspective assessments based on human cognition. Liu[26] developed a quantum based multi attribute decision making model for making E-commerce recommendations. Mukherjee[27] proposed a novel MCDM based on quantum in solar site selection. Mandal et al[28] formulated quantum inspired MUTLIMOORA method in green supplier selection. Mandal[29] combined quantum principles with TODIM and PROMTHEE II I renewable energy selection. Wu et al[30] developed a group-based quantum decision

model to study the interference effects in linguistic distribution. Yan et al[31] proposed multi-attribute quantum group decision making model considering the risk attitude of the decision maker. Awan et al[32] proposed fuzzy AHP based quantum decision making on the challenges of computing in the software industry. Xiao et al[33] developed a quantum integrated VIKOR decision making model. Dincer et al[34] proposed quantum spherical fuzzy hybrid modelling for analysing investments in circular economy. These quantum-based works describe the integrated methods evolved by combining quantum with MCDM methods.

The research gaps identified from the above-described literature are presented as follows

- Applications of MCDM methods are limited to electrical material selection considering the attributes of smart and sustainability
- Plithogenic based MCDM are not much explored in material selection
- Lack of integrated Plithogenic based Quantum decision-making approach.

This has motivated the authors to develop a more comprehensive and novel decision-making model considering the integration of Plithogenic logic with quantum decision making. The objective of this paper is to formulate an innovative and adaptive decision-making model to rank the alternatives based on attribute values. The efficacy of this developed approach is demonstrated with special reference to electrical material selection. Electrical materials shall be classified as conductors, semiconductors, superconductors, insulators and so on based on the attributes of material type and functional role in the electrical systems. This classification together with the subjective judgements of the experts together intensifies the constraints of choosing optimal electrical materials. To address such challenges, a more resilient decision-making approach is essential and this research work attempts in developing an integrated model conjoining both Plithogenic logic and quantum theory.

The other contents of this study are organized into the following sections. The methodology of the integrated Plithogenic quantum decision making method is described in section 2. The newly developed hybrid method is applied to the decision-making problem of electrical material selection in section 3. The sensitivity analysis is performed and the results are discussed in section 4. The last section concludes the work with future research insights.

2. Mathematical Model

This section explains the steps followed in the newly developed hybrid approach of Plithogenic quantum in ranking the electrical materials.

Step 1: Problem Definition

The decision-making problem is well defined with the alternatives say E_1, E_2, \dots, E_m and the criteria. In this case, the criteria are refereed as attributes say $C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_n$. In addition, with these attributes, the attribute values are also considered for each of the attributes say $C_{11}, C_{12}, \dots, C_{1k}, C_{21}, \dots, C_{2j}, \dots, C_{n1}, C_{n2}, \dots, C_{nt}$.

Step 2: Choosing Dominant Attribute Value and assigning Linguistic Degrees of appurtenance

The dominant attribute values corresponding to each of the attributes are chosen. Also, a table of linguistic degrees of appurtenance relating all the attribute values with the alternatives is prepared. The contradiction degree between the dominant and other attribute values are also tabulated.

Attribute Values	E1	E2	Em
C11	L111	L112	L11m
C12
:
:
:
Cnt	Lnt1	Lnt2	Lntm

Step 3: Quantification of Linguistic Variable

The linguistic variables are quantified using either fuzzy, intuitionistic or neutrosophic numbers based on the decision- making environment.

Step 4: Construction of Plithogenic accuracy matrix

The Plithogenic accuracy matrix $PA = [p_{ij}]$ is constructed using Plithogenic accuracy function given by $d(a_{ij}F_g) + d(a_{ik}, F_g) * c(a_{ij}a_{ik})$ ----- (1)

Where $d(a_{ij} F_g)$ represents either fuzzy, intuitionistic or neutrosophic association degree between the attribute values and the course of actions, $d(a_{ik} , F_g)$ is pertaining to the dominant attribute values and $c(a_{ij} a_{ik})$ is the contradiction degree.

Step 5: Normalization of the matrix

The Plithogenic accuracy matrix is normalized to obtain $PN = [pn_{ij}]$

For benefit attributes: $pn_{ij} = \frac{p_{ij}-min(p_{ij})}{max(p_{ij})-min(p_{ij})}$ ----- (2)

For cost attributes: $pn_{ij} = \frac{max(p_{ij})-(p_{ij})}{max(p_{ij})-min(p_{ij})}$ ----- (3)

Step 6: Weighted Normalized Matrix

The weighted normalized matrix $P_W = [pw_{ij}]$ is obtained by multiplying the weights of the attributes with the normalized matrix.

Step 7 : Compute the final Preference state

The final preference state $|s\rangle$ is a quantum superposition of all weighted attribute- based state vectors: $|s\rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_j |s_j\rangle}{\|\sum_{i=1}^n w_j |s_j\rangle\|}$ ----- (4)

Here, $|s_j\rangle$ represents the **preference vector** of an alternative derived from its attribute values and w_j is the weight of the attribute. This step is important as it conjoins all decision information into a single, normalized preference state, combining the influence of dominant attribute values and their associated degrees.

Step 8: Compute Quantum Probability q_j for each alternative

The quantum probability q_j for each alternative is given by: That is, the square of the inner product of $|s_j\rangle$ with the final state $|s\rangle$. This gives the probability of the alternative j in the final preference state which serves as the basis for ranking the alternatives.

Step 9: Ranking of the Alternatives

The alternatives are ranked based on the probability values. The alternatives with higher probabilities are given priorities.

3. Illustration of Plithogenic Quantum in Electrical Material Selection

Problem Description

Let us consider a decision-making problem of ranking the alternatives considering the attributes of electrical efficiency, thermal stability, environmental impact, economic viability and smart system compatibility attributes or the criteria are considered for ranking the alternative. However, in Plithogenic based decision-making, the attribute values are considered in addition to the attributes. Also, both the degrees of appurtenance and contradictions are also considered. The attributes and the attribute values are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Attribute Values

Attributes	Attribute Values		
Electrical Efficiency (C1)	Legacy Standard (C11)	Industry Average (C12)	Advanced Performance (C13)
Thermal Stability (C2)	Limited (C21)	Improved (C22)	High (C23)
Environmental Impact (C3)	Carbon- neutral (C31)	Partially sustainable (C32)	Eco- optimized (C33)
Economic Viability (C4)	Premium (C41)	Cost-disruptive (C42)	Economical (C43)

Smart System Compatibility (C5)	Incompatible (C51)	Partial (C52)	Complete (C53)
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The dominant attribute values under each attribute are C13, C23, C31, C42 and C53. The attribute values expected to be satisfied by the alternatives are considered as the dominant attribute values. The alternatives considered for this study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Alternatives of the Decision- making

E1 Gallium Nitride (GaN)
E2 Silicon Carbide (SiC)
E3 Graphene
E4 High-Temperature Superconductors (HTS)
E5 Recyclable Aluminum Alloys (Al Alloys)
E6 Biodegradable Insulation Materials (BIM)
E7 Hybrid Ceramic-Polymer Dielectrics (HD)
E8 Perovskite

The classification of the alternatives is presented in the figure 1.

Fig. 1. Classification of Electrical Materials.

The linguistic degree of satisfaction of the alternatives to the attribute values are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Linguistic representations of the Alternatives and Attributes Values

Attribute Values	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8
C11	L	L	L	L	M	M	L	L
C12	M	M	M	M	H	M	M	M
C13	H	H	VH	VH	L	L	H	H
C21	L	L	L	VL	M	M	L	H
C22	M	M	M	M	H	M	M	M
C23	H	VH	H	VH	L	L	H	L
C31	M	M	M	M	H	VH	H	M

C32	H	H	H	H	M	M	M	H
C33	M	M	H	M	M	VH	H	H
C41	H	H	H	VH	L	M	M	M
C42	M	M	M	L	H	H	M	H
C43	L	L	L	VL	H	H	M	H
C51	L	L	L	M	L	H	L	M
C52	M	M	H	H	M	M	M	M
C53	H	H	VH	M	M	L	H	H

The linguistic data is collected from the experts in the field of electrical engineering using a structured questionnaire. The contradiction degrees between the dominant and other attribute values are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Degrees of Contradictions between Attribute Values

Attributes	Dominant Attribute Values	Degree of Contradiction		
		C11	C12	C13
C1	C13	C21	C22	C23
		1/3	2/3	0
C2	C23	C31	C32	C33
		2/3	1/3	0
C3	C31	C41	C42	C43
		0	2/3	1/3
C4	C42	C51	C52	C53
		2/3	0	1/3
C5	C53	C11	C12	C13
		2/3	1/3	0

The initial decision making consisting the alternatives and the dominant attribute values is considered as follows in Table 5.

Table 5. Initial Decision- Making Matrix

Alternative / Attribute	C13	C23	C31	C42	C53
E1	H	H	M	M	H
E2	H	VH	M	M	H
E3	VH	H	M	M	VH
E4	VH	VH	M	L	M
E5	L	L	H	H	M
E6	L	L	VH	H	L
E7	H	H	H	M	H
E8	H	L	M	H	H

The attribute values C31 and C42 are cost and others belong to benefit criteria. Using fuzzy representations and applying the steps 4-8, the scores obtained are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Fuzzy Ranking Scores

Methods	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8
Fuzzy probability scores	0.0049	0.027	0.017	0.007	0.289	0.385	0.064	0.158
Rank	5	6	7	8	2	1	4	3

4. Sensitivity analysis

The ranking results obtained using Plithogenic quantum with fuzzy representations are discussed with intuitionistic and neutrosophic numbers. The results obtained are presented in the Table 7.

Table 7. Comparison of Ranking Results

Methods	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8
Intuitionistic probability scores	0.142	0.141	0.035	0.036	0.183	0.184	0.143	0.151
Rank	5	6	8	7	2	1	4	3
Neutrosophic Probability Scores	0.1460	0.1440	0.1325	0.1340	0.1720	0.1750	0.1505	0.1550
Rank	5	6	8	7	2	1	4	3

The ranking of the alternatives obtained under different representations are compared to demonstrate the consistency of the results. The graphical representation of these score values is presented in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. Comparison of Probability Scores.

On other hand, the criterion weights shall be varied based on the different dimensions of enhancing the efficiency of the electrical systems. The above ranking results are obtained considering equal weights, reflecting the necessity of all the attributes in material selection. The same decision-making problem shall also be discussed under different weights based on the perspectives of the manufacturing sectors.

Conclusion

This research work proposes a novel integrated method of Plithogenic based quantum. The newly developed method is applied in electrical material selection. This method is more effective in handling conflicting attributes and intricacies in decision making. The linguistic representation of the appurtenance degree is more realistic and it is quantified using fuzzy, intuitionist and neutrosophic numbers. The consistency of the ranking results is checked under different representations. This method shall be discussed under other Plithogenic MCDM methods. This work has several industrial applications as it contributes to energy optimization. The optimal selection of the electrical materials considering the attributes of electrical efficiency, thermal stability, compatibility, cost effectiveness and sustainability will certainly contribute to resilient energy system.

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